

QOBILIYAT VA IMKONIYATNI IFODALOVCHI MODAL FE'LLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur ishda qobiliyat va imkoniyat ma'nolarini ifodalovchi modal fe'llarning semantik va funksional xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ingliz tilidagi can, could, may, might kabi modal fe'llarning nutq jarayonida shaxsning ichki qobiliyati, tashqi sharoitga bog'liq imkoniyati hamda ehtimollikni ifodalashdagi o'rni yoritiladi. Shuningdek, ushbu modal fe'llarning o'zbek tiliga tarjimadagi muqobillari va ma'no nozikliklari qiyosiy jihatdan ko'rib chiqiladi. Natijada modal fe'llarning kommunikativ vazifasi va ularning til tizimidagi ahamiyati aniqlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: modal fe'l, qobiliyat, imkoniyat, can, could, may, might, ehtimollik, semantika, tarjima, qiyosiy tahlil

“Can” va “May” modal fe'llari shart va xohish-istak mayli formalariga ega. Ularning buyruq mayli hozirgi va o'tgan zamon formalarida ifodalanadi.

Xohish-istak mayli formasi buyruq maylidagi o'tgan zamon formasiga omonimdir. (Could, might)

“Can” modal fe'li quyidagilarni ifodalaydi:

- Real imkoniyat, jismoniy qobiliyatni bu holda “can” infinitivning noperfekt formasi bilan qo'llaniladi:

Present

He can translate, can not he?

It is wonderful how little a man can do alone.

But limited minds can recognize limitations only in others

Past

I could hear his voice so I knocked

At any rate he knew he could write it better now.

He could not walk very fast.

“Can” modal fe'lining ekvivalenti jismoniy qobiliyat ma'nosida “to be+infinitive” bo'ladi.

“Yet he was unable to move”. (U hali ham qimiray olmasdi).

Voqelikni sharotidan kelib chiqqan holdagi taxminiy imkoniyatni ifodalaydi. Bu holda infinitivning noperfekt formasi bilan qo‘llanishda “can” kelajakda bo‘ladigan taxmini ifodlaydi.

“What time is it? She asked”. “Quarted to one”, said Yates. “We can in Luxemburg tonight”. (Bugun kechqurun Lyuksemburgda bo‘lishimiz kerak).

Shart maylini “could” ifodalaydi: infinitivning noperfekt formasi bilan past darajadagi taxminga imkoniyat berilganligi, ba‘zan xushmuomala bilan so‘rashni ifodalaydi¹.

“Could you do it for me?” (Menga shuni qilib bera olasizmi?)

“If I have to give an answer right this minute the answer obviously is no, but if you could wait», he went on, «I wouldn’t ask for anything more”. (Agar kuta olganingda, davom etdi u, men boshqa xech narsa so‘ramagan bo‘lardim).

Perfekt bilan qo‘llanilganda “could” haqiqatda bo‘lmagan, hayol qilingan imkoniyatni ifodalaydi.

“You could have told me about long before”. (Buni menga avvalroq aytsangiz bo‘lar edi).

“Can” (could) modal fe‘llari infinitiv perfekt formasi bilan birgalikda bir ishni qilishda (odatda inkor gaplarda) imkoniyat bo‘lishiga shubha borligini ifodalaydi.

“Can” bilan birgalikda (buyruq mayli), “Could” formasidan ko‘ra (shart mayli) past darajadagi shubhani ifodalaydi.

“I should think there never can be have been a man who enjoyed his profession more than Mr Creakle did”. (Hech qachon Mister Kriklddek kasbidan xursand odam bo‘lmagan bo‘lsa kerak deb o‘ylardim).

“And, indded, she did feel there was something deep in it, though she couldn’t have put the feeling into words”. (U baribir xissiyotlarini so‘z bilan ifodalay olmasa ham, uning his tuyg‘ularida chuqur bir narsa bor edi).

“He was not old, he could not have been more than forty”. (U qirqdan oshmagan bo‘lsa kerak).

“May” modal fe‘li.

“May” fe‘li “Can”dan farqli ravishda, real qobiliyat yoki imkoniyatni o‘zini emas, balki taxmin yoki imkoniyatga yo‘l qo‘yilganligini ifodalaydi.

1. Imkoniyatga yo‘l qo‘yilganligi; ma‘lum bir sharoitda imkoniyatga hech qanday hayratli narsa yo‘qligini bildirib turadi. Agar sodir bo‘lsa, hech hayron bo‘ladigan joyi yo‘q.

¹Maugham S. The Moon and Sixpence. – Moscow: Penguin books, 1975. – P. 266.

“Friends may meet, but mountains never”. (Do ‘stlar uchrashishlari mumkin, lekin tog ‘lar yo ‘q)².

“A few moments may change our character for life”. (Bir necha daqiqalar hayotdagi rolimizni o ‘zgartirib yuborishi mumkin).

Farqi:

“May” va “Can” (real imkoniyat va imkoniyatga yo‘l borligi).

“You may break the body, but you can not break the spirit”. (Sen tanani sindirishing mumkin, lekin ko ‘ngilni buza olmaysan).

“Very” - is an adverb of degree and may modify an adjective or an adverb: but it can not modify a verb. (Very – sifat yoki ravishni anglatishi mumkin, lekin fe‘lni anglatmaydi).

“A fool may ask more questions than a wise man can answer”. (Axmoq donodan javob bera olishdan ko ‘ra ko ‘proq savol berishi mumkin).

“May” fe‘lining ma‘nolaridan biri bu ruxsat, hodisaning sodir bo‘lishiga imkoniyat borligini bildiradi.

“May I come in? certainly you may”. (Kirsam maylimi? Ha mumkin.).

2. Ishonchsiz bo‘lgan taxmin (maybe, perhaps, possibly): «Erik says that you may be coming to New York». (Erik seni Nyu Yorkka kelishing mumkin deyapti).

“He may be in the house now, said he cabman”. (U hozir balki uydadir, dedi aravakash).

“May” ning bu ma‘nosi infinitivning davomiy ko‘rinishdagi formasida, shuningdek davomiy ko‘rinishda qo‘llanilmaydigan (to be, to happen) fe‘l infinitivi oddiy formasida yaqqol ko‘rinadi:

“He must be at home” - ishonch.

“He may be at home” - ishonchsizlik alomatlari bo‘lgan taxmin.

Yuqori darajali taxmin ma‘nosi quyidagi birikmalar bilan ifodalanishi mumkin.

“To be sure” + infinitive

“To be certain” + infinitive

“But he is sure to marry her” (Lekin u albatta unga uylanadi).

“Later they had thought he was certain to die”. (Keyinroq uni o‘limga maxkum deb o‘ylashardi).

Taxmin ma‘nosi “to be likely + infinitive” birikmasi bilan ifodalanishi mumkin.

“I’m not likely to see you again, he said slowly” (Men seni yana ko ‘rmasam kerak).

“May” taxmin ma‘nosida infinitiv perfekt formasi bilan qo‘llaniladi.

²Maugham S. The Moon and Sixpence. – Moscow: Penguin books, 1975. – P. 266.

“I may have spoken a bit too strongly, said David”. (Men oz-moz o‘tkirroq gapirib yuborgan bo‘lishim mumkin).

“Might” birikmasi (shart mayli formasidagi “may” fe’li) infinitiv noperfekt formasi bilan tasodifiy imkoniyatga yo‘l qo‘yilganligini anglatadi (balki, shunday, bo‘lishi mumkin).

“*He said he might be coming in*”. (U kelib qolishi mumkinligini aytdi).

“*Might? said Erik bitterly*”. “*Was that all he said?*”. (Mumkin? dedi Erik achchiqlanib. Bu aytganlarni hammasimi?)

“*Does it ever strike you that I might be interested*”. (Qiziqib qolishim mumkinligi hayolingga kelmadimi?)

Farqi: “May” – “Might”

“*Don’t waste the money. Time may come when you might need it*”. (Pulni bekorga sarflama! Sen unga muxtoj bo‘lib qoladigan payt kelishi mumkin).

Farqi: “Could” – “Might”

“*I could earn a dollar and a half a day, common labour and might get in as instructor. I say “might” mind you, and I might be chucked out for sheer inability*”.

(Men yarim kunda umumiy ish ko‘rsatuvchi sifatida bo‘lishim mumkin edi va bir dollar ishlay olardim. Men “mumkin” deganimga ahamiyat ber. Picha qobiliyatsizligim uchun aldanib qolishim mumkin edi)³.

“Might” infinitiv noperfekt formasi bilan birgalikda ishning sodir bo‘lishiga ruxsat so‘rashni ifoda qiladi.

“*Might I see your wife for a minute?*” (Xotiningni bir daqiqaga ko‘rsam maylimi?)

“Might” infinitiv perfekt formasi bilan birgalikda ishga imkoniyatni o‘ylab ko‘rishni, shuningdek yuqori darajadagi noaniq va shubhali taxmini ifodalaydi. (Kim biladi, balki shunday).

“*A man who might have made an admirable ambassador in the seventeenth century is unlikely to prove anything but a laughing – stock today*”. (Kim biladi o‘n yettinchi asrda qoyilmaqom bo‘lgan kishi hozir kulgi bo‘lishdan boshqa hech narsani isbotlay olmasa kerak).

“*Somebody might have found us in the end*”. (Balki bizni kimdir oxirida topgan bo‘lishi mumkin)⁴.

“*I’ve been wondering where I might have heard it*”. (Qayerda buni eshitgan bo‘lishim mumkinligiga hayronman). “*I don’t know how long the silence lasted. It might have been for half an hour*”. (Bilmayman bu sukunat qancha davom etdi, balki yarim

³William W. Dad. – New York: Penguin books, 1987. – P. 311.

⁴Buranov J. Ingliz tili grammatikasi. – Tashkent: “O‘qituvchi”, 1973. – B. 84.

soatdir). Infinitiv perfekt formasi bilan “might” birikmasi sodir bo‘lishning imkoniyati yo‘q, taxmin qilingan ishni ham ifodalash mumkin.

“Had she fourteen instead of twenty four, she might have been changed by then”. (Yigirma to‘rt emas, qirq bo‘lsa ham, uni o‘shanda o‘zagartirish mumkin edi).

“To be to+infinitive”

Ba‘zan ish – harakatni amalga oshirishda imkoniyat ma‘nosini majhul nisbat formasida infinitiv birikmasida “to be to” fe‘li bilan ham ifodalash mumkin.

“The book is to be found at any bookstore”. (Bu kitobni har qanday kitob bo‘limidan topish mumkin). Binobarin shu birikma zaruriyatni ifodalash mumkin, bu holda kontekstni hisobga olish zarur.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI

1. Maugham S. The Moon and Sixpence. – Moscow: Penguin books, 1975. – P. 266.
2. Buranov J. Ingliz tili grammatikasi. – Tashkent: “O‘qituvchi”, 1973. – B. 84.
3. William W. Dad. – New York: Penguin books, 1987. – P. 311.
4. Abdulaziz Abduxalimov. Ingliz tili modal fe‘llarining tipologik talqini // ИЖТИМОЙ-ГУМАНИТАР ФАНЛАРНИНГ ДОЛЗАРБ МУАММОЛАРИ АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ГУМАНИТАРНЫХ НАУК Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences. Volume 5– 2025, – P. 183-188